

The Role of Teachers in Digital Self-Efficacy

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Abstract. This purpose of the study was to determine which domains of teacher's role significantly influence the digital self-efficacy of teachers. A total of 82 teachers in Binugao District, Davao City Division were identified through tabachnick and fidell formula. The study utilized a descriptive-correlation design. An adapted survey questionnaires were utilized which centered on teacher's role in digital self-efficacy and digital self-efficacy of teachers. Mean, Pearson r, and regression analysis were used as statistical tools of the study. Results revealed on the level of teacher's role in digital self-efficacy in terms of knowledge, skills, relationship of students, and teacher's experience was high. Moreover, on the level of digital self-efficacy of teachers in terms of information and data literacy, communication and collaboration, safety, and problem-solving. Clearly, the findings inferred a strong significant relationship between teacher's role and the digital self-efficacy of teachers. Based on the result of the analysis, all of the domains of the teacher's role significantly influenced the digital self-efficacy of teachers. Thus, this study suggests that teachers should actively seek professional development opportunities that strengthen their technological, pedagogical, and content knowledge. By reflecting on their teaching experiences and student interactions, they can further enhance their confidence in using digital tools effectively, as supported by the TPACK framework.

KEY WORDS

1. Teacher's Role 2. digital self-efficacy 3. descriptive correlational

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1. Introduction

In the past decade, technology and science have experienced tremendous progress, mostly propelled by the emergence of artificial intelligence as well as the creation of advanced digital devices. These developments have significantly influenced numerous sectors, including education. Nonetheless, despite the prevalent utilization of digital technologies in education, some educators struggle with digital self-efficacy, or belief in one's ability to proficiently employ technology to attain goals for learning. Inadequate digital self-efficacy within educators is an escalating issue, as it may obstruct the compre-

hensive adoption of technology in educational settings, hence restricting its wide range of benefits.

A similar condition was noted among educators in the Davao region. Teachers were reluctant to incorporate digital technology due to the required preparation. Furthermore, they exhibited a lack of confidence in utilizing technology. They regarded themselves as beginner in technological implementation. In addition, they had restricted options for technological training. This hesitation was further exacerbated by limited access to updated digital tools and infrastructure

in their schools. Consequently, many educators felt overwhelmed by the rapid shift to digital learning environments (Camarillo, 2024).

Despite extensive global research on teachers' digital self-efficacy, there exists a gap regarding studies in local settings, such as in Binugao District of Davao City Division. Furthermore, the influence of teachers' role on digital self-efficacy is occasionally overlooked in research that emphasizes broader variables or elements. While numerous studies investigate teacher roles or digital self-efficacy separately, there is a paucity of research that analyzes the direct correlation between these two factors. Assessing the relationship between teachers' roles and their perceived digital self-efficacy may yield valuable information for focused professional development initiatives and skill enhancements.

The study pursued answers to the ensuing objectives: a.) to determine the level of the teachers' role in digital self-efficacy in Binugao District, Davao City Division in terms of knowledge, skills, relationship of students, and teacher's experience. b.) to determine the level of digital self-efficacy of teachers in Binugao District, Davao City Division in terms of information and data literacy, communication and collaboration, safety, and problem-solving. c.) to determine if there is significant relationship between teachers' role and digital self-efficacy of teachers in Binugao District, Davao City Division, and d.) to determine which domain of teachers' role significantly influences the digital self-efficacy of teachers in Binugao District, Davao City Division.

At .05 level of significance, the following hypotheses were tested: a.) There is no significant relationship between teachers' role and dig-

ital self-efficacy of teachers in Binugao District, Davao City Division. b.) None of the domains of teachers' role significantly influences the digital self-efficacy of teachers Binugao District, Davao City Division.

This study offered valuable insights for multiple stakeholders by emphasizing the impact of teachers' roles on their digital self-efficacy. For school heads, it informed the design of targeted professional development programs; for teachers, it highlighted personal strengths and areas for growth, encouraging collaboration and tailored learning. Students benefited from more confident and effective technology use in classrooms, leading to enhanced learning experiences. Finally, the study laid a foundation for future research, offering a framework for exploring factors that influenced teachers' technology use and supporting the development of best practices in digital education.

1.1. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework of the Study—The conceptual framework, as illustrated in Figure 1, included the variables of the study. It demonstrated that the independent variable of the study was teachers' roles, specifically assessed in terms of knowledge, skills, relationships with students, and teacher experiences. On the other hand, digital self-efficacy served as the dependent variable, measured in terms of information and data literacy, communication and collaboration, safety, and problem-solving. The conceptual framework emphasized the potential relationship between teachers' roles and digital self-efficacy. It provided a comprehensive lens through which the study assessed how teachers' roles interacted with their perceptions of their technical capabilities.

2. Methodology

The following section outlines the procedures used by the researcher to perform this research study. It includes the population and sampling, instrumentation, data source, and data analysis.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Fig. 1. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework

2.1. Research Design—This study adopted a quantitative methodology, specifically a descriptive-correlational design, to explore the relationship between teachers’ roles and their digital self-efficacy in Binugao District, Davao City Division. It assessed teachers’ roles in terms of knowledge, skills, student relationships, and experiences, alongside their digital self-efficacy in areas like data literacy, communication, safety, and problem-solving. While not establishing causality, the approach identified patterns and associations between instructional roles and confidence in using digital tools. The findings offer insights to help teachers improve their digital competencies and guide schools and policymakers in designing effective professional development for digital education.

2.2. Ethical Consideration—This study strictly followed ethical principles outlined by RMC’s Research Ethics, prioritizing integrity, confidentiality, and informed consent. It aimed to explore how teachers’ roles influenced their digital self-efficacy in Binugao District, offering valuable insights for educators, school heads, and policymakers. Participants were

fully informed of the study’s purpose, ensured anonymity, and could withdraw anytime without consequence. While risks were minimal, measures were taken to protect participants’ privacy and well-being. The researcher, qualified and guided by academic mentors, accessed adequate facilities and adhered to the Data Privacy Act of 2012. Safeguards against conflicts of interest, unequal treatment, and bias were upheld, with transparent communication and dissemination of findings.

2.3. Research Respondents—The study focused on teachers in Binugao District, Davao City Division, using Tabachnick and Fidell’s (2007) formula to determine a sample size of 82 respondents based on four independent variables: knowledge, skills, student relationships, and experiences. Simple random sampling was used to ensure fairness and reduce bias, enhancing the generalizability of findings. Inclusion criteria required participants to be current teachers in the district who actively used digital tools, while those not meeting these standards were excluded. This approach ensured relevant, accurate data to explore the impact of teachers’ roles on their digital self-efficacy. Data were collected through a structured survey question-

naire specifically designed to measure the identified variables and assess teachers' perceptions of their digital competencies.

2.4. Research Instrument—This study used an adapted and validated survey questionnaire to assess teachers' roles and digital self-efficacy in Binugao District, Davao City Division. Based on Paredez-Aguirre et al. (2024), the 40-item tool measured four dimensions—knowledge, skills, student relationships, and experiences—using a five-point Likert scale. The second part assessed digital self-efficacy

2.5. Data Gathering Procedure—This study followed a systematic data collection process, beginning with formal permission from institutional authorities and school heads to ensure ethical compliance and transparency. The survey instrument, adapted and validated by experts, underwent content validation and a pilot test with 30 teachers to refine clarity, reliability,

2.6. Data Analysis—The study used statistical tools to address its research questions: the mean measured the levels of teachers' roles and digital self-efficacy; Pearson r assessed the

across information and data literacy, communication and collaboration, safety, and problem-solving. The instrument underwent expert validation, a pilot test, and achieved a high reliability index (Cronbach alpha = .88), ensuring its accuracy in evaluating the relationship between teachers' roles and digital competence. The validated tool provided comprehensive insights into how various aspects of teachers' roles influenced their confidence and capability in using digital technologies effectively.

and relevance. Questionnaires were administered face-to-face to foster trust, clarify doubts, and encourage thoughtful responses, enhancing data quality. Completed surveys were carefully reviewed for completeness and securely stored to maintain confidentiality. Data were analyzed using SPSS, ensuring rigorous statistical treatment and adherence to institutional standards for validity and reliability.

relationship between these two variables; and multiple linear regression identified which specific domains of teachers' roles significantly influenced their digital self-efficacy.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter emphasized the findings and discussion of the research. The presentation commenced with a descriptive examination of the level of the teachers' role in digital self-efficacy and the level of digital self-efficacy of teachers, then addressing the association between these two factors. The lecture concluded with the discussion of the domain of teachers' role that significantly influences the digital self-efficacy of teachers in Binugao District, Davao City Division.

3.1. Level of Teachers' Role in Digital Self-Efficacy—Table 1 showed the summary of the level of teachers' role in digital self-efficacy which was measured by four indicators namely: knowledge, skills, relationship of students, and teacher's experience. The mean ratings of these indicators were as follows: Relationship of Stu-

dents (3.48) was classified as high. Skills (3.43) was described as high. Knowledge (3.42) was categorized as high. Lastly, Teacher's Experience (3.40) was described as high. The overall garnered mean was (3.43) which was also described as high. This means that the level of teachers' role in digital self-efficacy in terms of

knowledge, skills, relationship of students, and Binugao District, Davao City Division. teacher's experience was oftentimes evident in

Table 1. Summary on the Level of Teachers' Role in Digital Self-Efficacy

No.	Item	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Knowledge	3.42	High
2	Skills	3.43	High
3	Relationship of Students	3.48	High
4	Teacher's Experience	3.40	High
Overall Mean		3.43	High

Legend: 1.00 – 1.79: Very Low 1.80 – 2.59: Low 2.60 – 3.39: Moderate 3.40 – 4.19: High 4.20 – 5.00: Very High

3.2. *Level of Digital Self-Efficacy of Teachers*—Table 2 showed the summary of the level of digital self-efficacy of teachers which was measured by four indicators namely: information and data literacy, communication and collaboration, safety, and problem-solving. The mean ratings of these indicators were as follows: Communication and Collaboration (3.55) was classified as high. Information and Data Literacy (3.45) was described as high. Problem-solving (3.44) was also categorized as high. Lastly, Safety (3.42) was described as high. The overall garnered mean was (3.47) which was also described as high. This means that the level of digital self-efficacy of teachers in terms of information and data literacy, communication and collaboration, safety, and problem-solving was oftentimes evident in Binugao District, Davao City Division.

Table 2. Summary on the Level of Digital Self-Efficacy of Teachers

No.	Item	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Information and Data Literacy	3.45	High
2	Communication and Collaboration	3.55	High
3	Safety	3.42	High
4	Problem-solving	3.44	High
Overall Mean		3.47	High

Legend: 1.00 – 1.79: Very Low 1.80 – 2.59: Low 2.60 – 3.39: Moderate 3.40 – 4.19: High 4.20 – 5.00: Very High

3.3. *Significant Relationship between Teachers' Role and Digital Self-Efficacy of*—Table 3 displayed the data on the significant relationship between teachers' role

and digital self-efficacy of teachers in Binugao District, Davao City Division. The Pearson Product-Moment Correlation (Pearson r) was used to analyze the association between the two variables. The analysis yielded a r-value of 0.89 which was described as strong correlation and a p-value of .000, which is below the .05

threshold for significance. As a result, the null hypothesis was rejected, confirming a meaningful correlation between the teachers' role and their digital self-efficacy. This suggests that the way teachers engage in their roles may directly influence their confidence in using digital tools effectively.

Table 3. Significant Relationship between Teachers' Role and Digital Self-Efficacy of Teachers

Variables	Relationship	r-value	Statistical Description	p-value	Decision
Teachers' Role (x)	Digital Self-Efficacy of Teachers (y)	0.89	Strong Correlation	.001	Reject H ₀

Note: Significant at $p < 0.05$.

3.4. *Domains of Teachers' Role that Significantly Influence Digital Self-Efficacy of Teachers*—Table 4 presents the results of a regression analysis examining the relationship between different aspects of the teacher's role—specifically knowledge, skills, student relationships, and teacher's experience. The analysis produced a computed r-value of 0.89 and a p-value below 0.001, signifying a strong positive correlation among these variables (Cohen et al., 2002). These findings lead to the rejection of the null hypothesis, which posited no significant relationship between the teacher's role and their digital self-efficacy, thereby confirming a high level of correlation as observed in the study.

The results distinctly reveal a very strong and significant relationship between the teacher's role and their digital self-efficacy. The analysis yielded an F-value of 65.54 with a

p-value of less than 0.001, indicating that the model is statistically significant. Furthermore, the R² value of 0.7921 implies that 79.21 percent of the variation in teachers' digital self-efficacy is accounted for by the identified predictors, while the remaining variation is due to factors outside the scope of the four dimensions of the teacher's role.

The regression coefficients reveal that all domains of teachers' role significantly influence digital self-efficacy of teachers. Among these domains, the relationship of students, with an unstandardized coefficient of =0.424, exhibited the most significant influence on digital self-efficacy of teachers, as evidenced by p-values below 0.05. Consequently, this result leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis. These findings highlight the teacher's role in digital self-efficacy, particularly a positive classroom environment, play in mitigating disruptive digital use.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

Table 4. Domains of Teacher’s Role that Significantly Influence the Digital Self-Efficacy of Teachers

Teacher’s Role	B	Beta	Standard Error	t-value	p-value	Decision
Constant	1.897	–	.209	4.668	.000	–
Knowledge	.378	.102	.085	1.086	.001	Reject H ₀
Skills	.397	.601	.076	6.432	.000	Reject H ₀
Relationship of Students	.424	.605	.084	6.234	.000	Reject H ₀
Teacher’s Experience	.365	.502	.069	5.647	.000	Reject H ₀

Dependent Variable: Digital Self-Efficacy of Teachers

R = 0.89 R² = 0.7921 F-ratio = 69.856 p-value = .000

Significance Level: *p* <0.05

4.1. *Findings*—The findings of this study are as follows: the level teacher’s role in digital self-efficacy in terms of knowledge, skills, relationship of teachers, and teacher’s experience. Also, the level of digital self-efficacy of teachers in terms of information and data literacy, communication and collaboration, safety, and problem-solving. Moreover, the significant relationship of teachers’ role and the digital self-efficacy of teachers. Lastly, the domains of teacher’s role that significantly influence digital self-efficacy of teachers in Binugao District, Davao City Division:

4.2. *Conclusions*—On the level of teacher’s role in digital self-efficacy in terms of knowledge, skills, relationship of students, and teacher’s experience revealed a mean score equivalent to high, which also means that the level of teacher’s role in digital self-efficacy was oftentimes evident. This indicates that teachers consistently demonstrate active engagement in shaping students’ digital learning experiences. This result reflects Bandura’s Self-Efficacy Theory, which suggests that personal beliefs, informed by experience and social interaction, strongly influence individuals’ confidence in their ability to succeed in specific tasks, including digital instruction.

On the level of digital self-efficacy of teachers in terms of information and data literacy, communication and collaboration, safety, and problem solving revealed a mean score equivalent to high, which also means that the level of the digital self-efficacy of teachers was oftentimes evident. This finding implies that teachers are generally equipped and confident in using digital tools for instructional purposes. It supports the TPACK Framework, which highlights how the integration of technological, pedagogical, and content knowledge enhances teachers’ proficiency and comfort in applying digital tools effectively in teaching and learning processes.

On the test of relationship between variables, this strong positive relationship affirms the relevance of Self-Determination Theory (SDT), which explains how the fulfillment of competence, autonomy, and relatedness influences motivation and self-belief. The result suggests that the more empowered teachers feel in their roles, the more confident they become in their digital abilities.

Based on the regression analysis, the findings reveal that all examined domains of the teacher’s role namely: knowledge, skills, relationship with students, and teaching experience—significantly influence teachers’ dig-

ital self-efficacy. This supports Bandura’s Self-Efficacy Theory, emphasizing that positive interpersonal experiences, such as strong student-teacher relationships, can significantly strengthen a teacher’s belief in their digital competence and instructional effectiveness.

4.3. *Recommendations*—Based on the study’s findings, it is recommended that the Department of Education implement ongoing digital training programs grounded in frameworks like TPACK and Self-Efficacy Theory to enhance teachers’ knowledge, skills, and student engagement strategies. School heads should

foster collaborative, supportive environments that encourage mentoring and innovation in digital teaching, aligned with Self-Determination Theory. Teachers are encouraged to pursue professional development and reflect on their experiences to strengthen their confidence in using technology. Students should engage actively with digital tools and provide feedback to support effective instruction. Future researchers may explore the long-term effects of professional development or examine institutional support for digital competence through qualitative and longitudinal studies.

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